

Teacher's Readiness On The Integration Of Artificial Intelligence In Teaching: A Basis For An Intervention Plan

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a transformative force in education, enhancing teaching and learning through intelligent systems, personalized instruction, and improved efficiency. As higher education institutions adopt technological innovations, teachers play a critical role in successfully integrating AI into instructional practices. This study assessed the extent of readiness of teachers in integrating AI in their teaching practices at University of Cagayan Valley during the academic year 2024–2025, serving as a basis for a proposed policy input.

The researcher used descriptive-correlational research design, involving 139 faculty members selected through stratified sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and correlation statistics. The findings revealed that faculty members demonstrated a high extent of readiness, behavioral intention, and perceived benefits, while their attitude toward AI integration was moderate. Age and civil status showed significant relationships with AI integration, whereas other profile variables were not significant. Key concerns identified include overreliance on AI, accuracy and reliability issues, data privacy and ethical concerns, and lack of training and knowledge. The study concludes that although faculty members are generally ready and willing to integrate AI into teaching, challenges related to attitudes, ethics, and technical competence persist. Therefore, continuous institutional support, targeted training programs, and clear policy guidelines are necessary to ensure the effective, ethical, and sustainable integration of AI in education.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, teacher readiness, AI integration, behavioral intention, attitudes, perceived benefit*

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly recognized as a transformative technology in education, with its potential to enhance teaching and learning experiences through intelligent systems and personalized learning pathways. Additionally, AI is the most important technology of recent times. The integration of AI in education is not merely a technological advancement; it represents a paradigm shift in how education is delivered and experienced. As educational institutions worldwide explore the potential of AI to enhance teaching and learning, the role of teachers in adopting and integrating AI into their instructional practices has gained significant attention.

According to UNESCO (2021) the potential of AI is to innovate teaching and learning practices, ultimately accelerating progress in education. Moreover, AI in education not only enhances students' computational thinking skills but also creates new ways to engage learners (National Science Foundation 2023). Additionally, AI integration holds significant potential to improve educational outcomes and align teaching practices with global standards, particularly the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), such as Quality Education (SDG 4) and Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure (SDG 9). By fostering an adaptive and inclusive educational environment, the integration of AI can contribute to equitable access to quality education and support lifelong learning opportunities for all.

AI's potential to revolutionize teaching and learning is profound. AI can enhance the quality of education by providing personalized learning experiences, improving student engagement, and enabling more effective resource management. Study Conducted by Zawacki-Richter et al., (2019) shows that AI-driven platforms can adapt instructional content to match individual student learning styles, provide real-time feedback, and identify at-risk students.

In terms of the benefits of AI, many studies have shown the positive benefits of it. Study shows by Luckin, R., & Holmes (2016) that AI can lead to more efficient learning processes, higher student satisfaction, and better academic outcomes. Furthermore, AI's ability to support data-driven decision-making helps educators and administrators optimize their efforts, making the educational process more effective and responsive to student needs.

In addition, teacher readiness is a critical factor in the successful integration of AI into educational practices. Readiness in this context refers to the extent to which teachers are willing and able to incorporate AI into their teaching. This readiness is influenced by several factors, including teachers' attitudes toward AI, their behavioral intentions to use AI, and their perceptions of AI's benefits and challenges. Research has shown that Teachers' digital competence is associated with their attitudes toward AI, moreover, teachers show a high level of willingness to use AI in their teaching as a tool. (Galindo-Domínguez et al., 2024).

A study by Polak et al. (2022), has shown that a positive attitude towards AI education, combined with high motivation to introduce AI-related content at school, translates into a strong positive willingness factor. Thus, positive attitudes towards AI are often associated with a readiness to adopt new technologies in teaching practices, while negative attitudes, which may

stem from concerns about job displacement, ethical considerations, or a lack of understanding of AI, can hinder the adoption of AI in educational settings.

A legal framework also further supports the integration of AI in education, which is the Republic Act No. 10650, or the Open Distance Learning Act, which emphasizes the role of technology in expanding access to education. In addition, in 2019, the Republic enacted technological development, including the field of AI, as outlined in Republic Act No. 11293, or the Philippine Innovation Act (PIA), which declared its state policy to foster innovation as a vital component of national development and sustainable economic growth. It also recognized the importance of an effective and efficient innovation ecosystem, and that this requires the government to implement the “whole of government” approach to ensure policy coherence, alignment of priorities, and effective co-ordination in program delivery.

Moreover, Republic Act No. 11899 also known as the Second Congressional Commission on Education Act II, is to enhance the skills and competitiveness of the Philippine workforce in human and digital technology and innovations. Furthermore, Republic Act No. 11930, the Philippine Digital Workforce Competitiveness Act, prioritizes the adoption of digital transformation in education and institutionalizes educational reforms in response to the so-called Fourth Industrial Revolution. However, this Republic Acts has its regulations on the use of AI in the Philippines using the lens of data privacy/data protection.

Furthermore, Department of Education’s (DepEd) policies on ICT integration and the Commission on Higher Education’s (CHED) advocacy for innovative teaching practices align with the push for AI-enabled education. These legal bases provide a strong foundation for every institution to incorporate AI into its educational mission.

The University of Cagayan Valley (UCV), one of the private higher education institutions in Region II offering diverse programs, aims to become internationally recognized. A key requirement for global competitiveness is adopting technology-assisted teaching and learning, which means faculty must equip themselves with technological advancements, especially artificial intelligence (AI).

However, observations show that while some educators, particularly from older generations, recognize AI's potential, others raise concerns about challenges like technical complexity, inadequate training, and ethical issues. Although UCV has drafted a policy on AI use, it remains unapproved for implementation, especially in instructional settings.

Hence, in this study, the researcher aimed to assess teachers’ readiness for integrating artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching, drawing on their perspectives to inform program interventions. Specifically, it would assess teachers’ readiness, attitudes, behavioral intentions, perceived benefits in teaching, and concerns about adopting AI technologies. Analyzing these factors, the research would identify areas for improvement and would develop targeted recommendations such as training and seminars to enhance teacher competence in AI integration.

The findings would benefit teachers by equipping them with essential skills and knowledge for effective AI use, while supporting the university's goals of delivering innovative, high-quality education.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the extent of Readiness of teacher in integrating artificial intelligence in their practices at University of Cagayan Valley, Tuguegarao City, Cagayan for the School year 2025-2026, as a basis for a proposed policy input.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Civil Status
 - 1.4 Number of Relevant Training/Seminars Attended
 - 1.5 Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.6 Length of Service
 - 1.7 Faculty Rank
2. What is the extent of readiness of the teachers in integrating Artificial Intelligence in their teaching practices relative to:
 - 2.1 Readiness
 - 2.2 Behavioral intentions; and
 - 2.3 Attitudes towards integrating AI
 - 2.4 Perceived Benefits
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of readiness on the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in teaching among teachers and their profile variables?
4. What are the issues and concerns encountered by the respondents regarding the readiness of teachers on integration of artificial intelligence in teaching?
5. What intervention plan can be crafted to address the issues and concerns encountered by the respondents regarding integration of artificial intelligence in teaching?

METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Research Design

This study made use of a quantitative research design, specifically a descriptive-correlational design. According to Bhat (2018), descriptive-correlational research explained the relationships between two or more variables without making claims about cause and effect. Thus, this design suited the study as it described faculty members' profile variables and the extent of artificial intelligence (AI) integration in their teaching practices. Moreover, it was utilized to determine the relationships between the extent of AI integration among faculty members and their profile variables.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were full-time faculty members at the University of Cagayan Valley (UCV) who taught at the college level during the 2024–2025 school year. They were selected using Stratified Random Sampling to determine the sample size per college. According to Hayes (2024), stratified random sampling divides a population into smaller subgroups, or strata, ensuring proportional representation.

The table below shows the distribution of respondents per college:

Table 1

Distribution of the Respondents

College	Population(N)	Sample(n)
School of Liberal Arts and Teacher Education	88	57
College of Criminal Justice Education	48	31
College of Information Technology	9	6
College of Technology	6	4
College of Hospitality Management	13	8
School of Business Administration and Governance	4	3
College of Maritime Education	14	9
College of Engineering	14	9
College of Health	15	10
College of Social Work	3	2
Total	214	139

Data Gathering Tool

This study utilized a questionnaire checklist to gather data on teachers' readiness for artificial intelligence (AI) integration in teaching.

The first part was constructed by the researcher and consisted of faculty members' profile variables, including age, sex, civil status, number of relevant trainings/seminars attended, highest educational attainment, length of service, and faculty rank.

The second part was adopted from Badiah N. M. Alnasib (2023) in her study titled, “Factors Affecting Faculty Members’ Readiness to Integrate Artificial Intelligence into Their Teaching Practices: A Study from the Saudi Higher Education Context.” This part comprised four sections: readiness (6 items), attitudes (7 items, with items 3, 4, and 5 reverse-scored), behavioral intentions (5 items), and perceived benefits of AI in teaching (14 items).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher underwent the following procedures prior to the conduct of the study:

First, upon approval from the Graduate School Office and Institutional Review Board (IRB), the researcher wrote a letter to the University President through the Director of the Human Resources Development Office (DHRDO) to request the list of full-time faculty members from various colleges as respondents.

Second, the researcher wrote letters to the Deans of the different colleges, noted by the research adviser and Dean of the Graduate School, to secure permission for questionnaire administration.

Third, the researcher personally administered the questionnaires to respondents, informing them of the study’s objectives. Participation was voluntary with no monetary compensation; respondents completed the questionnaire in 10–15 minutes after providing informed consent.

Lastly, after retrieval, the researcher tabulated and statistically analyzed the data. All information was kept confidential in adherence to data privacy laws and used solely for academic purposes.

Statistical Tools

The researcher used the following statistical tools to attain the objectives of the study:

Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution were used to determine the profile variables of the respondents.

Weighted mean was utilized to assess the readiness of teachers in the integration of AI into their teaching practices.

To further interpret the mean, below is the 5-point Likert scale used:

Numerical Scale	Mean Range	Degree of Agreement
5	4.21-5.00	Very High Extent
4	3.41-4.20	High Extent
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Extent
2	1.81-2.60	Low Extent
1	1.00-1.80	Very Low Extent

Chi-square Cramer's V and Pearson r test were utilized to examine the relationship between the extent of integration of artificial intelligence in teaching among the faculty and their profile variables.

Additionally, Frequency and Rank were utilized to determine the issues and concerns encountered by the faculty members regarding the integration of artificial intelligence into teaching.

Summary of Findings

In light of the results and discussion of the, the following are the key findings:

1. Profile of the Respondents
 - Majority of the respondents are 21-30 years old, female, single, with 3 and below attended relevant training, most have units in a Master's Degree, majority have rendered 3 years and below in teaching, and with the majority of assistant instructor teaching position.
2. Extent of integration of Artificial Intelligence in teaching among the faculty members.
 - 2.1 Readiness
 - The faculty members are ready to integrate AI into their teaching to a "High Extent."
 - 2.2 Attitude
 - Faculty members demonstrate a moderate extent of attitude toward AI integration in teaching.
 - 2.3 Behavioral Intentions
 - The faculty members demonstrate a high extent of intention to use AI in their teaching.
 - 2.4 Perceived Benefits
 - The faculty members perceive the benefits of AI in teaching to a high extent.
3. Correlation between the extent of integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in teaching among faculty members and their profile variables

- The faculty members' age shows a significant and negative relationship in the extent of integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in teaching in all the dimensions.
 - The faculty members' civil status shows a significant relationship, particularly with readiness and the behavioral intention on the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in teaching.
4. Issues and concerns encountered by the respondents regarding the integration of artificial intelligence in teaching
- The major issues or concern encountered by the faculty members in the integration of AI in teaching are, Overreliance and Student Dependency on AI, Accuracy, Validity, and Reliability, Data Privacy, Security, and Ethical, and Lack of Training and Knowledge

Conclusion

Based on the study findings, the researcher concludes that faculty members demonstrate a high extent of readiness and willingness to integrate Artificial Intelligence (AI) into their teaching practices, indicating a positive direction toward technological adoption in education. However, personal factors such as age and civil status, along with moderate levels of attitude, suggest that full acceptance is not yet fully realized. Additionally, concerns related to ethics, reliability, and limited training highlight existing challenges that may affect effective implementation. Therefore, while AI integration shows promising progress, it requires continuous institutional support, targeted training, and clear guidelines to ensure its effective, ethical, and sustainable use in teaching.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations based on the conclusion drawn:

1. School Administrators should develop and implement a comprehensive AI policy that outlines ethical standards, responsible use guidelines, and data privacy protections.
2. The HRDO should conduct continuous professional development, workshops, and certification courses on AI integration to enhance faculty competence particularly for senior faculty members who may require additional technical support.
3. Faculty Members may design assessments that promote critical thinking and minimize excessive student dependency on AI and guide the students in verifying AI-generated content.
4. School Administrators may adopt the intervention plan crafted as a basis in crafting the AI policy in the school
5. Students should be oriented on ethical and responsible AI usage, including proper citation, disclosure of AI assistance, and critical evaluation of AI outputs.
6. Future Researchers may widen the scope of the study since this is limited to faculty members who are teaching in the Tertiary level of the University, and are encouraged to conduct a qualitative part of the study.

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